

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

Difficulty reading

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

**Difficulty
understanding
complex text
without
supporting
images**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More integrated
features like
images?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

Difficulty writing

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

Difficulty with spelling

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

Difficulty with punctuation and grammar

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

**Difficulty
reading and
following
instructions**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

Difficulty filling out forms

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

Difficulty finding information

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

Difficulty dealing with text in foreign languages

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

**Difficulty
understanding
what is fake
news and what
is accurate**

Existing tools

news

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Reading, Writing and Comprehension

**Difficulty
answering
calls due to
not being able
to read caller**

ID

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Help?

